

Environmental Accounting in Ethiopian Manufacturing Industries: Opportunities and Challenges for Sustainable Development

¹Salahedin Abdu Ebrahim*, ²Prof. Jaladi Ravi

Research Scholar, Department of Commerce and Management Studies, Andhra University,
Andhra Pradesh, India.

DOI: - 0009-0002-0299-219X

Research Director, Professor, Head Department of Commerce and Management Studies,
Andhra University, Andhra Pradesh, India.

Received: Feb 28, 2026

Accepted: Mar 31, 2026

Published: Apr 04, 2026

Abstract

Environmental accounting is a strategic tool for sustainable development in developing economies like Ethiopia, where manufacturing and mining pressure natural resources. This study, using data from 2025, assessed the awareness, opportunities, challenges, and governmental roles in promoting environmental accounting within the MIDROC Investment Group. A descriptive cross-sectional survey was conducted among 347 employees from manufacturing and mining units, yielding 316 valid responses (91.07% response rate). Data from a structured questionnaire were analyzed using descriptive statistics. Results showed a high awareness of environmental accounting (Mean > 3.80). Respondents strongly agreed it delivers significant benefits: cost savings (M=4.62), improved regulatory compliance (M=4.57), enhanced corporate image (M=4.59), and better risk management (M=4.40). Key challenges were managerial difficulties (M=4.17) and a lack of standardized frameworks (M=3.99). Governmental roles were deemed essential, with strong support for mandatory environmental reporting (M=4.41), financial incentives (M=4.06), and support for empirical research (M=4.30). The study concludes that environmental accounting holds high strategic value for firms like MIDROC and underscores the urgent need for stronger institutional frameworks and government mandates to support its effective implementation.

Keywords: Environment, Accounting; Sustainability; Ethiopia; Manufacturing; Mining

1. Introduction

Climate change has emerged as a critical global development challenge, intensifying weather extremes and undermining socioeconomic progress. Ethiopia is particularly vulnerable to climate change impacts (MEFCC, 2015). Manufacturing and mining sectors are central to national economic growth in many countries (Qi et al., 2019), yet their operations often generate significant social and ecological pressures (Li et al., 2014) and exert direct stress on natural systems (Häyhä & Franzese, 2014).

Ethiopia possesses substantial potential for industrial expansion due to its diverse and largely untapped mineral resources (Mitchell, 2024). Its manufacturing sector is also rapidly growing, encompassing industries such as textiles, leather products, food processing, and pharmaceuticals, supported by industrial parks and fiscal incentives (Yanet, 2023). Despite this progress, the country continues to face serious environmental challenges. While environmental laws exist, industrial pollution remains a persistent problem, reflecting the difficulty of balancing economic advancement with ecological responsibility (Desta, 2017).

Within this context, manufacturing companies under the MIDROC Investment Group (MIG) have implemented certain corporate social responsibility initiatives, a component related to environmental accounting. However, full adoption of environmental accounting practices has

not occurred voluntarily. Given that environmental accounting enables organizations to quantify environmental costs and benefits, its application is vital for promoting sustainable development and aligning corporate activities with national and global sustainability objectives.

Empirical studies on environmental accounting in Ethiopian industrial enterprises remain scarce, leaving substantial knowledge gaps. This limited evidence base makes it difficult to understand emerging challenges in developing economies like Ethiopia, where environmental management concepts are not yet fully institutionalized. Accordingly, this study addresses a significant scientific problem: the lack of systematic understanding of the opportunities and challenges associated with implementing environmental accounting in the Ethiopian context, with a focus on the MIDROC Investment Group.

2. Literature Review

Growing global instances of natural disasters and environmental degradation have intensified societal expectations for environmentally responsible actions from both governments and corporations (Jatmiko et al., 2024). As environmental pressures increase, industries worldwide have turned toward environmental accounting as a strategic mechanism to strengthen sustainability outcomes and enhance accountability (Sharma, 2012).

Environmental accounting supports sustainable development by enabling firms to integrate economic, social, and environmental considerations (Tu & Huang, 2015), aligning with the broader framework of sustainable development (Hussain, Halim, & Bhuiyan, 2016).

With rising environmental awareness, organizations have increasingly adopted systems to assess and manage the ecological impacts of their operations. Green accounting assists firms in identifying, measuring, and reporting environmental effects (Iskandar et al., 2021), while practices that integrate financial, social, and environmental information contribute to stronger sustainability reporting and accountability (Ashari & Angora, 2021).

Through environmental disclosures, organizations communicate environmental stewardship and commitment to stakeholders (Sebastian, 2022). Neglecting environmental considerations can create significant risks for firms and society (Lako, 2018).

From a business perspective, environmental accounting includes reporting on greenhouse gas emissions, waste management, resource consumption, and energy efficiency within financial disclosures (Gonzalez & Peña-Vinces, 2023). It also supports strategic decision-making processes (Erstawan, 2024) and aligns with global sustainability priorities (Harianja & Riyadi, 2023).

These practices enable firms to demonstrate social and environmental responsibility (Sukmadilaga et al., 2023). However, the lack of universally accepted environmental accounting standards presents challenges for multinational companies (Lima et al., 2024; Lima et al., 2023).

Implementing environmental accounting often requires technological integration to collect, classify, and process environmental data (Leite et al., 2021). Barriers include high implementation costs, insufficient staff training, weak environmental legislation, inadequate government incentives, minimal regulatory penalties, and lack of tax incentives (Boiral et al., 2018).

Effective implementation requires supportive legal frameworks, managerial commitment, strong coordination, and clear guidance to avoid misallocation of environmental costs (Gale, 2006). Earlier reports also emphasize inadequate cost-tracking systems and weak environmental information structures as barriers (IFAC, 2005).

Despite such challenges, environmental accounting plays a global role in addressing climate change, resource depletion, and ecological degradation (Boiral et al., 2018). Yet awareness and adoption levels vary across countries. For example, private firms in the UK exhibit strong awareness, whereas SMEs in Indonesia lag significantly behind (Nofriadi et al., 2025).

In Saudi Arabia, firms struggle with classifying environmental costs and measuring environmental performance due to lack of standardization (Abubaker, 2024). In Jordan and the UAE, environmental awareness is high, but actual commitment and reporting performance remain low (Jahamani, 2023).

In many regions, environmental accounting creates opportunities for financial benefits, competitive advantage, improved risk management, innovation, and readiness for future regulatory shifts (Kenny et al., 2025). Chinese listed companies adopting environmental accounting have shown reduced carbon emissions and improved sustainability competitiveness (Chen & Li, 2024).

South Asian SMEs demonstrate improved innovation performance and enhanced waste-management practices through green accounting adoption (Patel & Sarker, 2024). In South Africa, however, adoption remains limited due to weak government support and lack of clear implementation guidelines (Nyahuna et al., 2023).

Several developing economies face widespread challenges. In India, institutional weaknesses and data shortages hinder implementation, despite opportunities in resource efficiency and green investment (Muley, 2022). Libyan manufacturing firms face management, informational, financial, and attitudinal barriers (Elhossade et al., 2022).

In Bangladesh, high costs, inexperienced labor, weak legal frameworks, and conceptual confusion impede adoption (Hossain, 2019). Similar issues appear in the industrial sector of Pune, where inadequate training and limited knowledge restrict green accounting practices (Mane, n.d.). Nigerian firms face challenges such as lack of reporting standards and resistance to organizational change (Faith, 2025).

Regional evidence further illustrates practical implications. Kenyan firms achieved cost reductions and enhanced sustainability performance by integrating environmental data into accounting systems (Okello & Wanjare, 2024). In Ethiopia's mining sector, operations have caused significant environmental damage—including water depletion, soil erosion, and ecosystem degradation—while accountability remains limited (Birhanu, 2022).

Evidence from Ethiopian manufacturing, textile, and garment industries demonstrates that sustainable practices contribute to improved economic performance and green innovation (Nigatu et al., 2024). Ethiopian textile firms adopting environmental accounting have shown improvements in water conservation, energy management, and reporting quality (Kassa & Demissie, 2025). Agro-processing companies in Ethiopia also benefit from environmental management accounting through reduced resource use and lower costs (Tsfaye & Mulugeta, 2023).

International evidence further supports the business value of environmental accounting. Vietnamese manufacturing firms report cost efficiency and process optimization through enhanced waste and energy management (Nguyen & Tran, 2022). Malaysian companies benefit from improved decision-making on pollution-control investments and energy management (Abdullah & Khalid, 2023).

Gulf corporations strengthen environmental compliance and data accuracy when integrating ICT technologies such as IoT and AI into environmental accounting systems (Al-Khalifa & Al-Mutairi, 2024). In North Africa, management support and strong regulatory enforcement emerge as predictors of adoption (Mohammed & Ibrahim, 2025). Stakeholder influence also plays a key role, as seen in Ghana where environmental reporting is shaped largely by stakeholder pressure (Agyemang, Appiah, & Boateng, 2022).

In conclusion, the literature demonstrates that environmental accounting contributes positively to sustainability, cost efficiency, and organizational accountability. However, adoption remains constrained by financial, technological, managerial, and regulatory challenges. These persistent barriers highlight the need for stronger institutional support and standardized frameworks to enhance the effectiveness of environmental accounting practices.

3. Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to examine the level of awareness, the challenges encountered, the opportunities available, and the role of government in implementing environmental accounting within the manufacturing and mining industries of the MIDROC Investment Group in Ethiopia.

4. Methods

A descriptive cross-sectional research design was employed to obtain a comprehensive understanding of environmental accounting practices in the selected sectors. The manufacturing and mining units of the MIDROC Investment Group were purposively selected due to their substantial ecological and economic importance in Ethiopia.

The study targeted employees directly involved in financial and environmental management processes, including accountants, finance managers, environmental officers, and senior management staff.

A census approach was applied to ensure complete coverage of the study population. Out of 347 eligible employees across the selected units, 316 completed and returned the questionnaire, resulting in a high response rate of 91.07%. Participant Characteristics: Because the study used a census method, which included all eligible members of the organization in the target units, demographic diversity was a natural part of the organizational structure. Participants were important organizational roles that were directly involved in the implementation of environmental accounting. Because the study used a census method, the sample reflected the organizational structure of the MIDROC manufacturing and mining units.

The questionnaire was developed using a systematic approach: (1) item generation based on existing frameworks for environmental accounting (Burritt & Christ, 2023; IFAC, 2005), adapted to Ethiopian regulations and reviewed by research director. The final version of the questionnaire consisted of 37 items and employed a five-point Likert scale and was divided into four constructs: awareness (6 items), benefits (11 items), challenges (13 items), and government role (7 items).

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire measured on a five-point Likert scale. Secondary data were obtained from scholarly articles, journals, and related literature to support interpretation and contextualization of findings.

Data analysis was conducted using SPSS version 27. Descriptive statistics were employed to summarize the findings and present them in tables. The reliability of the measurement scales was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha to ensure internal consistency.

5. Ethical Considerations

Prior to data collection, participants were fully informed about the purpose and scope of the study. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were assured that their information would be used solely for research purposes. Confidentiality was strictly maintained throughout the study. No names or identifying details were recorded, and all data were presented in aggregated form to ensure privacy and prevent identification of individual respondents.

6. Results

Table 1: Item-Total Statistics for reliability

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.783	37

The consistency of the indicators in the scales was evaluated using a Cronbach's Alpha test. Cronbach's alpha was applied to evaluate reliability for the survey, based on the sample estimate. Taber (2018) argued that an alpha value of 0.70 is a sufficient indication of dependability or internal consistency for an instrument. George and Mallery (2003) suggest 0.7

as the acceptable threshold. Cronbach's alpha for all entries in this table was 0.783, which is deemed highly satisfactory.

Table 2. Awareness of Environmental Accounting			
Item Statistics			
Awareness of Environmental Accounting			
	Mean	Std. Dev.	N
Do you think environmental accounting is essential for companies?	4.47	.500	316
Do you think environmental accounting influences a company's financial achievement?	4.08	.785	316
Do you think investors consider environmental factors when making investment decisions?	4.10	.814	316
Are you aware of the benefits of applying environmental accounting practices?	4.14	.747	316
Are you aware of any government regulations related to environmental reporting?	3.86	.848	316
I believe that integrating environmental accounting practices can contribute to Sustainable development.	4.31	.661	316

Source: - SPSS output 2025 G.C

The results from the table 2, provide clear insights into respondents' perceptions of the importance, benefits, and regulatory understanding of environmental accounting within the manufacturing and mining sectors of the MIDROC Investment Group. Overall, the findings indicate a consistently high level of awareness and positive attitudes toward environmental accounting.

Respondents strongly agreed that environmental accounting is essential for companies, reflected in a mean score of 4.47 with a standard deviation of 0.500. The perception that environmental accounting influences a company's financial achievement also showed strong agreement, with a mean value of 4.08 and a standard deviation of 0.785.

Additionally, participants believed that investors consider environmental factors when making investment decisions, yielding a mean score of 4.10 and a standard deviation of 0.814. Awareness of the benefits of applying environmental accounting practices was similarly high, demonstrated by a mean score of 4.14 and standard deviation of 0.745.

In contrast, familiarity with government regulations related to environmental reporting showed relatively lower awareness, with a mean value of 3.86 and standard deviation of 0.848, indicating room for improvement in regulatory communication or training.

Finally, respondents agreed that integrating green accounting practices contributes to sustainable development, as shown by a mean score of 4.31 and a standard deviation of 0.696. These results collectively demonstrate that employees possess strong conceptual and practical awareness of environmental accounting, particularly its importance, financial relevance, and sustainability benefits, while regulatory awareness remains moderate.

Table 3. Challenges of Environmental Accounting			
Item Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Dev.	N
Complexity of Measurement	3.94	.860	316
Increased costs of verification and audit due to the complex nature of accounting and the situation-specific basis of various standards.	3.84	.942	316
The absence of standardized frameworks for green accounting complicates comparisons between companies and industries.	3.99	.775	316
Data Availability and Quality.	3.65	.831	316

Integration with Financial Reporting.	4.07	.879	316
Regulatory Compliance.	3.74	.898	316
Organizational Resistance.	4.00	.851	316
Supply Chain Complexity.	3.72	.950	316
Lack of alignment between green accounting policies with other business objectives of the organization.	4.08	1.005	316
Need for trained personnel and researchers to identify the issues that can be resolved using green concepts and practices.	4.01	.730	316
The increasing complexity of the work environment.	3.64	1.040	316
Less attention from senior management.	2.96	1.132	316
Managerial challenges due to less qualified manpower, inexperienced staff, and a lack of coordination in implementing the policies.	4.17	.782	316

Source: SPSS Output 2025 G.C.

The descriptive statistics in Table 4.2 indicate that respondents generally perceive significant challenges in the implementation of environmental accounting across organizations. Mean scores for the identified challenges range from 2.96 to 4.17, reflecting varying degrees of agreement on their severity.

The highest-rated challenge is managerial difficulties arising from less qualified manpower, inexperienced staff, and lack of coordination ($M = 4.17$, $SD = 0.782$). This is followed closely by challenges related to lack of alignment between green accounting policies and other business objectives ($M = 4.08$, $SD = 1.005$), and integration of environmental information with financial reporting systems ($M = 4.07$, $SD = 0.879$).

Respondents also rated organizational resistance ($M = 4.00$, $SD = 0.851$) and the need for trained personnel to apply green concepts and practices ($M = 4.01$, $SD = 0.730$) as significant impediments. In addition, the absence of standardized frameworks for green accounting received a high mean score ($M = 3.99$, $SD = 0.775$), reflecting notable concern over comparability and consistency across firms and industries.

Other challenges such as complexity of measurement ($M = 3.94$, $SD = 0.860$), increased costs of verification and audit ($M = 3.84$, $SD = 0.942$), regulatory compliance ($M = 3.74$, $SD = 0.898$), and supply chain complexity ($M = 3.72$, $SD = 0.950$) also fall within the higher range of agreement.

Moderate levels of concern were reported regarding data availability and quality ($M = 3.65$, $SD = 0.831$) and the increasing complexity of the work environment ($M = 3.64$, $SD = 1.040$). The lowest rated challenge is lack of attention from senior management, with a mean of 2.96 ($SD = 1.132$), indicating comparatively lower agreement among respondents. Overall, the results demonstrate that organizations face substantial technical, managerial, and operational challenges in adopting and implementing environmental accounting practices

Item Statistics	Mean	Std. Dev	N
Benefits of implementing Environmental accounting practices			
Implementing environmental accounting practices can lead to cost savings for manufacturing industries.	4.62	.624	316
Environmental accounting helps manufacturing industries ensure compliance with environmental regulations and standards.	4.57	.689	316
Enhanced Corporate Image.	4.59	.672	316
Risk Management.	4.40	.919	316
Resource Efficiency.	4.50	.507	316

By integrating environmental accounting into their operations, manufacturing industries can work towards long-term sustainability goals.	4.29	.649	316
Stakeholder Engagement.	4.10	.741	316
Enhanced Environmental Performance.	4.53	.687	316
By lowering pollution and promoting sustainable development, environmental accounting enhances the working environment of the company.	4.30	.662	316
Environmental accounting can act as an effective tool for ecological taxation by taxing organizations based on their environmental performance instead of their financial performance.	3.75	1.139	316
Environmental accounting can stimulate innovation in pollution control, conservation, and the reuse of resources.	4.15	.889	316

Source: SPSS output 2025 G.C

The results indicate strong agreement regarding the benefits of implementing environmental accounting practices in the manufacturing and mining sectors of the MIDROC Investment Group. Respondents reported that environmental accounting leads to cost savings, reflected in a high mean value of 4.62 and a standard deviation of 0.624, suggesting widespread recognition of its efficiency-enhancing role. Compliance with environmental regulations and standards was also strongly supported, with a mean score of 4.57 and a standard deviation of 0.689.

Participants perceived significant improvements in corporate reputation, as shown by the mean value of 4.59 and a standard deviation of 0.672 for the item “Enhanced Corporate Image.” Similarly, environmental accounting was viewed as beneficial for risk management, demonstrated by a mean score of 4.40 and standard deviation of 0.919.

Regarding resource-related outcomes, respondents agreed that environmental accounting enhances resource efficiency (M = 4.50, SD = 0.507). It also supports long-term sustainability goals (M = 4.29, SD = 0.649) and strengthens stakeholder engagement (M = 4.10, SD = 0.741). Positive perceptions of environmental performance were reflected in a mean value of 4.53 and a standard deviation of 0.687.

Respondents indicated that environmental accounting contributes to improving workplace environmental conditions, with a mean score of 4.30 and a standard deviation of 0.662. The potential for environmental accounting to act as a tool for ecological taxation received more moderate agreement (M = 3.75, SD = 1.139), suggesting varied perceptions of tax-related applications.

Finally, the belief that environmental accounting stimulates innovation in pollution control, conservation, and resource reuse was supported by a mean value of 4.15 and a standard

Table 5. Role of the government policy and Regulation			
Item Statistics	Mean	Std. Dev.	N
Role of the Government Policy and Regulation			
Governments often provide financial incentives and tax benefits to manufacturing companies that implement green practices.	4.06	.839	316
Requiring companies to collect data on environmental expenditures for statistical review.	4.41	.571	316
Providing Funding for empirical research to evaluate the status and potential of EMA.	4.30	.648	316
Establishing national prizes and competitions financed by governmental authorities.	4.47	.624	316

Organizing conferences, workshops, and working groups, bringing together experts from business, professional groups, government, NGOs, and academia to exchange knowledge and experience.	4.30	.730	316
Disseminating information through websites and electronic newsletters.	4.09	.918	316
Global Cooperation	4.43	.707	316

Source:- SPSS Output 2025 G.C.

Based on the above table 4, the results highlight strong agreement among respondents regarding the significant role of government in promoting and supporting environmental accounting practices.

The statement that governments often provide financial incentives and tax benefits to manufacturing companies adopting green practices received a mean value of 4.06 and a standard deviation of 0.839, indicating a generally positive perception of governmental financial support.

Respondents also strongly agreed that mandating corporations to gather data on environmental expenses for statistical analysis is an important governmental role, as shown by a mean of 4.41 and a standard deviation of 0.571.

Similarly, participants supported the idea of governments allocating resources for empirical research on Environmental Management Accounting (EMA), reflected in a mean score of 4.30 and a standard deviation of 0.648.

The establishment of national prizes and competitions funded by governmental authorities was highly regarded, with a mean value of 4.47 and a standard deviation of 0.624. Respondents also valued government-hosted conferences, workshops, and working groups aimed at knowledge sharing among corporations, experts, government bodies, NGOs, and academics (Mean = 4.30, SD = 0.730).

The dissemination of environmental accounting information through websites and electronic newsletters received agreement from respondents, as indicated by a mean score of 4.09 and a standard deviation of 0.918. Finally, the significance of global cooperation in advancing environmental management and accounting practices was strongly acknowledged, with a mean of 4.43 and a standard deviation of 0.707.

8. Discussion

The study's findings reveal a consistently high level of awareness and generally positive perceptions of environmental accounting among employees in the manufacturing and mining sectors of the MIDROC Investment Group. These results align with global evidence indicating that awareness is a key driver for the adoption of environmentally responsible practices within business enterprises (Alshehhi et al., 2018). Similarly, previous studies in India reported strong awareness of environmental accounting, demonstrating parallels between the Ethiopian context and other developing economies where environmental management concepts are becoming increasingly recognized (Joshi et al., 2022).

Although awareness levels were high, respondents demonstrated comparatively lower familiarity with government regulations on environmental reporting. This finding corresponds with evidence from Ethiopia showing that insufficient awareness of environmental policies and requirements weakens the implementation of sustainability initiatives (Desta, 2017). This suggests that even when organizations acknowledge the importance of environmental accounting, gaps in regulatory understanding may hinder effective implementation.

The perceived benefits of environmental accounting were also consistent with international research. Respondents highlighted advantages such as cost savings, improved corporate image, enhanced risk management, and stronger operational efficiencies benefits widely documented in empirical studies from countries such as China and the United States, where environmental management accounting has been shown to reduce inefficiencies and strengthen corporate reputation and stakeholder relations (Qian et al., 2018; Clarkson et al., 2011).

Respondents further emphasized environmental accounting's role in supporting sustainability goals, improving workplace conditions, and strengthening engagement with stakeholders. These findings align with global literature emphasizing the importance of environmental information in guiding pollution reduction, operational improvements, and long-term environmental performance (Choiriah, 2023).

Regarding governmental roles, respondents expressed strong expectations for institutional involvement through financial incentives, mandatory reporting requirements, support for research, and knowledge-sharing initiatives. These perceptions reflect international trends, including the European Union's Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD, 2024) and Non-Financial Reporting Directive (NFRD, 2014), which emphasize standardized environmental disclosures and institutional oversight.

Participants also recognized the importance of global cooperation in advancing environmental accounting. This aligns with international frameworks such as the UN System of Environmental-Economic Accounting (SEEA), which highlights the value of coordinated global efforts in developing harmonized environmental-economic reporting systems (United Nations et al., 2021). Studies further indicate that international climate agreements have strengthened the demand for robust environmental-economic accounting systems (Boiral et al., 2022).

The findings show that respondents perceive environmental accounting as a challenging practice shaped by technical, organizational, and strategic factors. The high means for measurement complexity, framework inconsistency, and integration difficulties indicate an overall recognition that environmental accounting still lacks the structural support needed for efficient implementation. This aligns with recent empirical evidence demonstrating that fragmented global sustainability standards and evolving measurement methodologies continue to hinder environmental reporting efforts (Khan et al., 2022; Qian & Schaltegger, 2023). Recent evidence shows that environmental metrics remain difficult to quantify due to evolving methodologies and data gaps (Qian & Schaltegger, 2023).

Respondents emphasized lack of trained environmental accounting professionals. Similarly, the strong emphasis on the need for trained personnel and managerial coordination reflects global research indicating that human resource capacity and internal expertise remain decisive factors in environmental accounting adoption (Adegbe & Olojede, 2024; Burritt & Christ, 2023). Recent evidence highlights skill shortages as a major barrier to adoption (Adegbe & Olojede, 2024).

Respondents identified poor alignment between sustainability goals and business strategies. Findings that internal culture and strategic priorities significantly influence the quality and extent of environmental disclosures (Camilleri, 2023). Research shows that without strategic alignment, environmental accounting yields limited benefits (Herzig & Schaltegger, 2022).

Respondents noted moderate agreement on regulatory and supply chain challenges is consistent with recent studies showing that expanding ESG regulations and complex supply networks create reporting burdens for firms (Testa et al., 2023; Tan et al., 2024). Respondents indicated that verifying environmental data increases audit expenses. Recent studies confirm that sustainability reporting increases audit time, technical requirements, and costs (Liu et al., 2024).

Meanwhile, Respondents moderately agreed that senior managers give low priority to environmental accounting. The lower score for senior management attention though still relevant reflects a trend in recent research that leadership involvement in sustainability has been improving over time but remains uneven across sectors (García-Sánchez & Martínez-Ferrero, 2023).

Respondents' concerns about organizational resistance are also validated by recent empirical work showing that internal cultural barriers, managerial attitudes, and competing priorities

continue to slow the adoption of environmental management accounting (Camilleri, 2023; Tan et al., 2024).

Respondents strongly agreed that lack of uniform standards creates reporting inconsistencies. This is supported by studies showing fragmented global ESG frameworks impede comparability (Khan, Serafeim & Yoon, 2022). Respondents agreed that meeting environmental regulations is challenging. Studies document increasing compliance burdens due to expanding sustainability regulations (Testa, Boiral & Heras-Saizarbitoria, 2023).

Concerns about integration with financial reporting reflect recent research showing that most companies continue to treat environmental data as a parallel system rather than embedding it into core financial decision-making, reducing its strategic usefulness (Herzig & Schaltegger, 2022; Stubbs, 2023).

Respondents reported difficulties accessing accurate environmental data. Empirical research shows environmental data quality remains inconsistent, especially in developing economies (Burritt & Christ, 2023). Respondents indicated that integrating environmental information with traditional accounting is difficult.

Respondents agreed that modern work environments add complexity to environmental accounting. Studies report that digitization, global supply chains, and climate disclosures increase complexity (Liu et al., 2024). Unqualified Manpower & Poor Coordination was the highest-rated challenge. Empirical studies show that lack of competent staff and weak internal coordination significantly reduce environmental disclosure quality (Burritt & Christ, 2023).

Overall, the discussion shows that although awareness of environmental accounting and its benefits such as improved sustainability performance, pollution reduction, operational efficiency, and long-term environmental management is growing, significant gaps remain in regulatory clarity, institutional support, skilled personnel, and standardized frameworks.

Strengthening government guidance, enhancing coordination with industries, and providing targeted capacity-building initiatives are essential to improve adoption and effectiveness, particularly in Ethiopia. These findings align with recent global literature, which underscores the need for strong institutional frameworks, stakeholder engagement, and international cooperation to advance environmental accounting practices and ensure meaningful sustainability outcomes.

9. Conclusion

The purpose of this study is to examine the level of awareness, the challenges encountered, the opportunities available, and the role of government in implementing environmental accounting within the manufacturing and mining industries of the MIDROC Investment Group in Ethiopia. This study aimed to assess awareness levels, implementation challenges, available opportunities, and the government's role in advancing environmental accounting within the manufacturing and mining divisions of the MIDROC Investment Group.

The results show that environmental accounting has become an important element of organizational decision-making, supporting better financial oversight, stronger regulatory alignment, and improved sustainability performance.

The findings suggest that environmental accounting contributes to long-term value creation by integrating environmental considerations into operational and strategic choices. Nonetheless, its broader adoption is limited by issues such as measurement difficulties, limited technical capacity, and the need for clearer regulatory direction.

Addressing these constraints will be essential for firms seeking to fully benefit from environmentally informed accounting systems. To strengthen business justification, Future research should explore sector-specific policy interventions and capacity-development strategies that can enhance environmental accounting implementation in developing economies. This study contributes empirical evidence from an African context and offers practical insights for policymakers, corporate leaders, and sustainability practitioners.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization: Mr. Salahedin Abdu and Prof Jaladin Ravi

Data curation: Mr. Salahedin Abdu and Prof Jaladin Ravi

Formal analysis: Mr. Salahedin Abdu and Prof Jaladin Ravi

Investigation: Mr. Salahedin Abdu

Methodology: Mr Salahedin Abdu

Project administration: Mr. Salahedin Abdu

Supervision: Prof Jaladin Ravi

Validation: Mr. Salahedin Abdu

Visualization: Mr. Salahedin Abdu

Writing – original draft: Mr. Salahedin Abdu

Writing – review & editing: Prof Jaladin Ravi

Acknowledgement(s):

I extend my heartfelt gratitude to the MIDROC Investment Group for their indispensable collaboration in supplying the critical data that underpinned this study. Their readiness to endorse academic investigation was crucial for the empirical foundation and success of this research.

Data Availability Statement

The survey instrument (questionnaire) and detailed methodology used in this study are available upon reasonable request.

Reference

- Abubaker, N. (2024). The role of environmental accounting in mitigating environmental pollution risk and its disclosure. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 9(10). <https://doi.org/10.38124/ijisrt/IJSRT24OCT032>
- International Federation of Accountants. (2005). Environmental management accounting.
- Adegbe, F. F., & Olojede, O. C. (2024). Environmental accounting competencies and sustainability reporting quality in developing economies. *Journal of Accounting and Sustainability*, 15(1), 22–39.
- Al-Qatwneh, A., Alqotaish, A. A., Al-Zoubi, K. M., & Al-Nsour, H. (2025). Green accounting and sustainable development: Empirical evidence from the industrial sector. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 18(2), 104.
- Alshehhi, A., Nobanee, H., & Khare, N. (2018). The impact of sustainability practices on corporate financial performance: Literature trends and future research potential. *Sustainability*, 10 (2), 494. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10020494>
- Alinda, A. (2024). Green product development and environmental safety in industrial sectors. *Journal of Sustainability Research*, 12 (2), 45–59.
- Alqotaish, A., & Qatawneh, A. (2025). The relationship between environmental accounting and financial performance in Jordanian industrial companies. *Perinatal Journal (Specialized Business Review)*, 33 (1), 312–325.
- Amad Ramdhani, B., & Prijanto, B. (2024). The effect of the implementation of green accounting on company value with profitability as a moderating variable. *Sanskara Accounting and Finance*, 3 (1), 33–43. <https://doi.org/10.58812/sak.v3i01.262>
- Baene, S. M. (2025). The role of Material Flow Cost Accounting (MFCA) in resource efficiency and waste reduction. *International Journal of Sustainability Accounting and Management*, 9 (1), 112–128.
- Bellucci, M., Simoni, L., Acuti, D., & Manetti, G. (2019). Stakeholder engagement and dialogic accounting: Empirical evidence in sustainability reporting. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 32 (5), 1467–1499.
- Boiral, O. (2018). Adoption and outcomes of ISO 14001: A systematic review. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 20(2), 411–432.
- Borges, T. (2022). Proposal for a model for the implementation of environmental accounting in the dairy industry. *Research, Society and Development*, 11(7), e29211729893.
- Burritt, R. L., & Christ, K. L. (2023). Environmental management accounting: Progress, challenges, and future pathways. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 412, 137673.
- Camilleri, M. A. (2023). Corporate sustainability reporting: Determinants, challenges, and developments. *Sustainability Accounting, Management and Policy Journal*, 14(2), 245–262.
- Cheng, L., Lin, Z., & Yang, X. (2025). Green innovation and firms' financial and environmental performance: The roles of pollution prevention versus control. *Journal of Accounting and Economics (Accepted/Online 2024/2025)*.
- Clarkson, P. M., Li, Y., Richardson, G. D., & Vasvari, F. P. (2011). Does it really pay to be green? Determinants and consequences of proactive environmental strategies. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 30(2), 122–144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaccpubpol.2010.09.013>

- Deb, S., Mukherjee, A., Chatterjee, P., & Vardhan, H. (2023). Minimizing waste and health damages through green production processes. *Environmental Management Review*, 31(4), 210–225.
- Desti, D. (2017). Industrial awareness of manufacturing sectors for sustainable environmental management in the case of Ethiopia Saris industrial area.
- Dr. Anand Muley. (2022). Green accounting: Challenges and opportunities in emerging economies. *Journal on Banking Financial Services & Insurance Research*, 12(11).
- Edward, O. F., Court, E. R., & Odey, J. O. (2025). Green accounting in Nigeria and Africa: Boosting sustainability with policies and incentive. *Journal of Accounting, Marketing and Management Research*, 12(2).
- Erstiawan, M. (2024). Mapping green accounting research trends in Indonesia: A systematic literature review perspective from 2017 to 2024. *GREENOMIKA*, 6 (2), 143–161. <https://doi.org/10.55732/unu.gnk.2024.06.2.5>
- Gale, R. (2006). Environmental costs at a Canadian paper mill: A case study of environmental management accounting (EMA). *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 14, 1237–1251.
- García-Sánchez, I. M., & Martínez-Ferrero, J. (2023). Leadership commitment and sustainability reporting quality: Global evidence. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 32(1), 150–163.
- Giannopoulos, A., & Fountoulakis, D. (2024). The impact of environmental management accounting on the environmental performance of SMEs: The mediating role of competitive strategy. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 33(2), 890–905.
- Gonzalez, C. C., & Peña-Vinces, J. (2023). A framework for a green accounting system exploratory study in a developing country context, Colombia. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 25 (9). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-022-02445-w>
- Harianja, N. W. C., & Riyadi, S. (2023). The effect of green accounting and good corporate governance on financial performance in chemical industry sub-sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) in 2018–2021. *Journal of Business Economics*.
- Häyhä, T., & Franzese, P. P. (2014). Ecosystem services assessment: A review under an ecological-economic and systems perspective. *Ecological Modelling*, 289, 124–132.
- Hendri Nofriadi, Rahma Yulida, & Pudji Astuty. (2025). A decade of green accounting in Indonesia and the UK: Implementation, challenges, and opportunities. *International Journal of Economics and Management Research*, 4(3). <https://doi.org/10.55606/ijemr.v4i3.554>
- Herzig, C., & Schaltegger, S. (2022). Environmental management accounting: A review of the current state and future directions. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 35(3), 710–736.
- Hossain, M. M. (2019). Environmental accounting challenges of selected manufacturing enterprises in Bangladesh. *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 7, 709–727.
- Hussain, M. D., Halim, M. S. B. A., & Bhuiyan, A. B. (2016). Environmental accounting and sustainable development: An empirical review. *International Journal of Business and Technopreneurship*, 6(2), 335–350.
- Iskandar, Setiawati, L., Diyanti, F., & Sari, D. M. (2021). Students' literacy on the green accounting concept and its challenges ahead. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 11(6). <https://doi.org/10.36941/jesr-2021-0146>
- Jahamani, Y. F. (2023). Green accounting in developing countries: The case of U.A.E. and Jordan. *Managerial Finance*, 29(8), 37–45. <https://doi.org/10.1108/03074350310768418>
- Otieno, J. O., & Wanjare, J. (2024). Role of environmental accounting in promoting sustainable business practice: A case study of Turkana County, Kenya. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.38124/ijisrt/IJISRT24MAY1016>
- Jatmiko, A., Irwansyah, I., & Khairin, F. N. (2024). Investigating the social and environmental accounting implementation in the reclamation of former mining sites: A case study of PT. Kitadin. *Journal of Madani Society*, 3(1), 156–170.
- Joshi, P. L., & Kumar, S. (2021). Environmental management accounting and risk management: An empirical analysis of Indian manufacturing firms. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 294, 126305. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.126305>
- Joshi, P. L., Kumar, S., & Muralidharan, S. (2022). Barriers to the adoption of environmental management accounting: An empirical investigation of manufacturing firms in India. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 314, 115074. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.115074>
- Kenny, R. N., Tatiane, A. S. B., Alline, B. M., Márcio, R. R., Maria do S. S. P., Haline, R. L. G., Deise Mara do N., Valdéria C. da S., Paulo D. P. F., Rodrigo A. D. de O., Eljalma A. B., Belmiro do N. J., & Maria L. S. M. O. (2025). Environmental accounting: Challenges and opportunities for organizations. *Revista de Gestão Social e Ambiental*. <https://doi.org/10.24857/rgsa.v19n4-040>
- Khan, M., Serafeim, G., & Yoon, A. (2022). Corporate sustainability: First evidence on materiality. *The Accounting Review*, 97(4), 185–216.
- Khan, S., & Gupta, S. (2025). Boosting the efficacy of green accounting for better firm performance: Artificial intelligence and accounting quality as moderators. *Meditari Accountancy Research*, 33(2), 472–496. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MEDAR-02-2024-2379>
- Koo, T. K., & Li, M. Y. (2016). A guideline for selecting and reporting intraclass correlation coefficients for reliability research. *Journal of Chiropractic Medicine*.

- Lako, A. (2017). Ecological crisis and the urgency of green accounting. *Majalah Akuntan Indonesia* (July–August), 1–11. DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21872.15361
- Leite, E. D., Gravina, D. N., & Santos, S. R. F. (2021). A importância do papel da contabilidade ambiental: Caso CEMIG. *RACE-Revista de Administração do Cesmac*, 9, 28–43.
- Li, Z., Ma, Z., van der Kuijp, T. J., Yuan, Z., & Huang, L. (2014). A review of soil heavy metal pollution from mines in China: Pollution and health risk assessment. *Science of the Total Environment*, 468–469, 843–853.
- Liu, G., & Guo, L. (2023). How does mandatory environmental regulation affect corporate environmental information disclosure quality? *Finance Research Letters*, 54 (3), 103702.
- Liu, J. Y., & Cho, C. H. (2024). Corporate environmental information disclosure and the moderating effect of stakeholder visibility. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*.
- Liu, Y., Zhang, H., & Wang, L. (2024). Audit implications of sustainability disclosures: Evidence from global ESG reporting. *International Journal of Auditing*, 28(1), 89–108.
- M., S. (2022). A study on green accounting: Concept and its importance. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, 10(8).
- Mahar, A. S., Zhang, Y., Sadiq, B., & Shahzad, F. (2025). Sustainability transformation through green supply chain management practices and green innovations in Pakistan's manufacturing and service industries. *Sustainability*, 17(5), 2204.
- Mane, D. A. (2023). A study of the challenges in implementing green accounting in the manufacturing organizations in Pune city.
- Mateusz Kurowski, & Katarzyna Huk. (2021). Corporate social responsibility and the mining industry: Areas of use and opportunities to reduce the negative effects of activity.
- Mencho, B. B. (2022). Assessing the effects of gold mining on the environment: A case study of Shekiso district, Guji zone, Ethiopia.
- Nazir, S., Zhaolei, L., Mehmood, S., & Nazir, Z. (2024). Impact of green supply chain management practices on the environmental performance of manufacturing firms considering institutional pressure as a moderator. *Sustainability*, 16(6), 2278.
- Ngepah, N., Saba, C. S., & Kajewole, D. O. (2024). The impact of industry 4.0 on South Africa's manufacturing sector. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 10 (1), 100226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joitmc.2024.100226>
- Nisaa, R. K., & Hidayati, C. (2025). The impact of green accounting and environmental performance on Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). *International Journal of Accounting Management Economics and Social Sciences*, 3(3), 1022–1032.
- Nugraha, A. (2023). Green accounting and sustainable development in the palm oil industry: Evidence from the Indonesia Stock Exchange. *Journal of Agricultural Sustainability*, 15 (3), 88–104.
- Portney, L. G., & Watkins, M. P. (2009). *Foundations of clinical research: Applications to practice* (3rd ed.). Pearson.
- Qi, R., Liu, T., Jia, Q., Sun, L., & Liu, J. (2019). Simulating the sustainable effect of green mining construction policies on the coal mining industry of China. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 226, 392–406.
- Qian, W., & Schaltegger, S. (2023). Environmental performance measurement and reporting: Current challenges and emerging solutions. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 331, 117243.
- Qian, W., Burritt, R., & Chen, J. (2018). The impact of environmental management accounting on firm performance: Evidence from Chinese manufacturing firms. *Sustainability*, 10 (11), 4171. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10114171>
- Sami Salem Elhossade, Akram Ali Zoub, & Ali Awad Zagoub. (2022). Barriers of environmental management accounting practices in developing country. *Risk Governance and Control: Financial Markets & Institutions*, 12 (1), 8–20. <https://doi.org/10.22495/rgcv12i1p>
- Sharma, N. J. (2012). Challenges and opportunities in implementing green accounting for sustainable businesses.
- Shrout, P. E., & Fleiss, J. L. (1979). Intraclass correlations: Uses in assessing rater reliability. *Psychological Bulletin*.
- Siti Choiriah, & Shanty Lysandra. (2023). Effect of green accounting, quality management on financial performance, and green innovation as moderation variables. *Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Studies*, 6 (7), 3534–3542. DOI: 10.47191/jefms/v6-i7-61
- Sklavos, G., Zournatzidou, G., Ragazou, K., & Sariannidis, N. (2025). Green accounting and ESG-driven eco-efficiency in European financial institutions.
- Songtao Xu, & Xia Chen. (2025). Government environmental information disclosure and digital transformation of manufacturing companies: Evidence from China. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 13, 1492874. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2025.1492874>
- Stanojevic, M., Vranes, S., & Gökalp, I. (2010). Green accounting for greener energy. In *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* (Vol. 14, Issue 9, p. 2473). Elsevier Ltd.
- Stubbs, W. (2023). Integrating sustainability into financial decision-making: Barriers and opportunities. *Sustainability Accounting, Management and Policy Journal*, 14(3), 458–475.

Sukmadilaga, C., Winarningsih, S., Yudianto, I., Lestari, T. U., & Ghani, E. K. (2023). Does green accounting affect firm value? Evidence from ASEAN countries. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 13 (2), 509–515. <https://doi.org/10.32479/ijeeep.13945>

Sumayyah, S., Damayanti, C. R., & Zahara, Z. (2025). Green innovation, green accounting, and performance: The moderating role of green intellectual capital. *Journal of Accounting and Investment*, 26 (2).

Tabasum, H. (2019). Issues and challenges of green accounting practices of small business enterprises. *Elk Asia Pacific Journal of Finance and Risk Management*, 10(3). DOI: 10.16962/EAPJFRM/ISSN.0976-7185/2015

Taber, K. S. (2018). The use of Cronbach’s alpha when developing and reporting research instruments in science education. *Research in Science Education*.

Tan, L., Testa, F., & Boiral, O. (2024). ESG supply chain pressures and environmental disclosure challenges. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 189(2), 345–362.

Testa, F., Boiral, O., & Heras-Saizarbitoria, I. (2023). Regulatory pressures and sustainability reporting burdens in global industries. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 32(4), 1890–1905.

Thomas Nyahuna, Mishelle Doorasamy, & Kiran Baldavoo. (2023). Barriers to implementation of environmental management accounting in South African small and medium enterprises for sustainable performance. *Indonesian Journal of Social and Environmental Issues*, 4(3), 258–266.

Tilahun Nigatu, Aschalew Degoma, & Abiot Tsegaye. (2024). Green practices and economic performance: Mediating role of green innovation in Ethiopian leather, textile, and garment industries in Ethiopia.

Toke, L. K., & Kalpande, S. D. (2024). The influence of green accounting on financial performance and corporate sustainability: A strategic perspective. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 410, 137–152.

Trevanti, R., & Yuliati, L. (2023). Empirical analysis of green accounting transformation in basic material sectors. *World Agricultural Economy*, 6(4), 98–115.

Tu, J. C., & Huang, H. S. (2015). Analysis of the relationship between green accounting and green design for enterprises. *Sustainability*, 7(5), 6264–6277. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su7056264>

Wang, L., Zhang, J., & Zhao, H. (2025). The impact of environmental tax reform on industrial green development: Evidence from China. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 13, 1593549.

Wang, T., & Ismail, K. (2025). The rise of management control systems: A systematic empirical analysis of EMA. *Sustainability*, 17(2), 842.

Wang, Y., Ummar, R., Qureshi, T. M., Ul Haq, J., & Bonn, M. A. (2025). Employee sustainability: How green practices drive employee well-being and citizenship behavior. *Sustainability*, 17*(3), 936. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17030936>

Yanet Fantaye Wogayehu. (2023). Brief look at the manufacturing industry of Ethiopia.

Yu, X., Mu, C., & Zhang, D. (2020). Assessment of land reclamation benefits in mining areas using fuzzy comprehensive evaluation. *Sustainability*, 12(5).

Zhang, Y., & Li, X. (2023). How do environmental regulations affect firm environmental performance? The mediating role of green accounting. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 30(10), 27087–27101.

Appendix

Questionnaires

No	Awareness of Green Accounting	SD	D	N	A	SA
1.	Do you think environmental accounting is essential for companies?	0	0	0	0	0
2.	Do you think environmental accounting influences a company's financial achievement?	0	0	0	0	0
3.	Do you think investors consider environmental factors when making investment decisions?	0	0	0	0	0
4.	Are you aware of the benefits of applying environmental accounting practices?	0	0	0	0	0
5.	Are you aware of any government regulations related to environmental reporting?	0	0	0	0	0
6.	I believe that integrating environmental accounting practices can contribute to Sustainable development.	0	0	0	0	0
No	Benefits of implementing green accounting practices	SD	D	N	A	SA
1.	Implementing green accounting practices can lead to cost savings for manufacturing industries.	0	0	0	0	0
2.	Green accounting helps manufacturing industries ensure compliance with environmental regulations and standards.	0	0	0	0	0

3.	Enhanced Corporate Image.	0	0	0	0	0
4.	Risk Management.	0	0	0	0	0
5.	Resource Efficiency.	0	0	0	0	0
6.	By integrating green accounting into their operations, manufacturing industries can work towards long-term sustainability goals.	0	0	0	0	0
7.	Stakeholder Engagement.	0	0	0	0	0
8.	Enhanced Environmental Performance.	0	0	0	0	0
9.	By lowering pollution and promoting sustainable development, green accounting enhances the working environment of the company.	0	0	0	0	0
10.	Green accounting can act as an effective tool for ecological taxation by taxing organizations based on their environmental performance instead of their financial performance.	0	0	0	0	0
11.	Green accounting can stimulate innovation in pollution control, conservation, and the reuse of resources.	0	0	0	0	0
No	Challenges of implementing green accounting practices	SD	D	N	A	SA
1.	Complexity of Measurement	0	0	0	0	0
2.	Increased costs of verification and audit due to the complex nature of accounting and the situation-specific basis of various standards.	0	0	0	0	0
3.	The absence of standardized frameworks for green accounting complicates comparisons between companies and industries.	0	0	0	0	0
4.	Data Availability and Quality.	0	0	0	0	0
5.	Integration with Financial Reporting.	0	0	0	0	0
6.	Regulatory Compliance.	0	0	0	0	0
7.	Organizational Resistance.	0	0	0	0	0
8.	Supply Chain Complexity.	0	0	0	0	0
9.	Lack of alignment between green accounting policies with other business objectives of the organization.	0	0	0	0	0
10.	Need for trained personnel and researchers to identify the issues that can be resolved using green concepts and practices.	0	0	0	0	0
11.	The increasing complexity of the work environment.	0	0	0	0	0
12.	Less attention from senior management.	0	0	0	0	0
13.	Managerial challenges due to less qualified manpower, inexperienced staff, and a lack of coordination in implementing the policies.	0	0	0	0	0
No	Role of the Government Policy and Regulation	SD	D	N	A	SA
1.	Governments often provide financial incentives and tax benefits to manufacturing companies that implement green practices.	0	0	0	0	0
2.	Requiring companies to collect data on environmental expenditures for statistical review.	0	0	0	0	0
3.	Providing Funding for empirical research to evaluate the status and potential for EMA.	0	0	0	0	0
4.	Establishing national prizes and competitions financed by governmental authorities.	0	0	0	0	0
5.	Organizing conferences, workshops, and working groups, bringing together experts from business, professional groups, government, NGOs, and academia to exchange knowledge and experience.	0	0	0	0	0

6.	Disseminating information through websites and electronic newsletters.	0	0	0	0	0
7.	Global Cooperation	0	0	0	0	0